

NERSC Technical Report no. 454

Technologies and collaboration for sustained Arctic Ocean Observing Systems (A00S)

D1: A00S guidance and requirement report

Map of the Arctic areas covered by the [Arctic Science Agreement](#) signed in 2017

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Executive summary

The AOOS project is a planning and collaboration project under the Arktis 2030 programme, with the goal to strengthening the Norwegian role in development of ocean observations in the Arctic. This report presents a snapshot of strategies, programmes and organizations addressing ocean observations in the Arctic, both in Norway and internationally. Ocean observation is important because it provides data which are important for climate, environment, food supply and other societal benefit areas on global, regional and local scale. Ocean observation in the Arctic is on the agenda of major international actors, in particular 1) The Arctic Council and its member states, organizations and working groups; 2) The European Union through its Arctic strategy and the Copernicus programme, which is the world's largest Earth Observation system using satellites; 3) The international Arctic research community represented by the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC). In addition, many international organisations, networks and fora have focus on developing ocean observation. The foremost of these are the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), the UN Decade of Ocean Science, and the G7 Future of the Seas and Ocean Initiative.

The report gives a summary of the Framework for Ocean Observing, established by GOOS in 2012. The Framework gives guidelines for establishing and operating ocean observing systems. A simple representation of an observing system consists of three parts: Input, Processes and Output. The input is represented by the requirements defined by the scientific disciplines and the societal issues (e.g. climate monitoring, ecosystem management, natural hazard warning). The processes include the observing activities using platforms and sensors to collect the data described by the requirements. The third component is the outputs, which are data products and information used in scientific work, services for society and in decision making. Finally, there is a feedback loop back to the requirements to be updated and improve the observing systems so they are relevant for the societal issues that help to formulated the requirements. The users and stakeholders of Arctic Ocean observations are briefly described as (1) scientists, (2) Public sector bodies, (3) Private sector – companies, (4) Non-governmental organisations, (5) Indigenous People and local community, (6) International bodies, organisations and networks, and (7) Media.

The requirements for ocean observations are defined by the Essential Ocean Variables (EOV), a global standard provided by GOOS. The methods to collect the EOVs can vary, but the quality of the data must satisfy requirements defined by various user communities. For example, the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) has prescribed measurement accuracy, spatial and temporal resolution and other technical specifications of the data to be used in climate monitoring. Observations in the Arctic follows the global standards, but logistical and infrastructure constraints make it difficult to collect in situ data in the same way as in other lower latitude oceans. The observing platforms and networks used on global scales are presented, and those that are applicable for the ice-covered areas are discussed more specifically.

Finally, digital technologies in the various parts of the observing systems, including data processing and management, have been described, but this topic will be further elaborated in a subsequent report in 2025.

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1. Introduction

The ongoing reduction of sea ice in the Arctic Ocean opens up new areas for tourism, fisheries, seafloor exploration, ship traffic and other economic activities. This leads to increased human presence in the Arctic, which will have impact on the environment. As a result there will be new requirements for planning and decision-making as a prerequisite for sustainable development in the region. This requires new knowledge about the ocean from surface to bottom based on research which needs new observations of environment and climate in the region. Today there is severe lack of *in situ* observations of the deep ocean under the sea ice, including the seafloor. This means that the research communities working with climate, weather, ice-ocean processes, seafloor research and geophysical hazards have limited knowledge about the processes below the sea ice. The lack of data limits the possibility of advancing research in this region, implying that knowledge-based management and decision-making cannot be done. It is therefore necessary to establish and sustain observing systems in the Arctic Ocean to support several scientific disciplines.

Norway as an Arctic nation has specific interest and responsibility in developing knowledge and competence about the northern areas which is necessary for safe and sustainable resource development, value creation and societal development. Norway has an ambition to be a leading nation in Arctic research, which will strengthen the management of environment and resources in the northern areas. Norway's strategy includes extending international cooperation in research to build more knowledge about the Arctic. An important of developing Arctic research is to establish and operate a long-term ice-ocean observing infrastructure, an Arctic Ocean Observing System (AOOS). Norway provides extensive resources to Arctic research, education and knowledge development through the University Centre in Svalbard (UNIS) and the SIOS Knowledge Centre (Fig. 1.1). Both these facilities are unique and give Norway a central role in research in the European sector of the Arctic. Furthermore, the icebreakers *RV Kronprins Haakon* and *KV Svalbard*, which operate in this area most of the year, have strengthened Norwegian capacity to conduct research in Arctic waters. With these resources Norway and collaborating countries have increased research activities in the region and have good possibilities to install long-term ocean observing infrastructure in the central Arctic Ocean.

Figure 1.1 Photograph of the Svalbard Science Park, where UNIS and SIOS Knowledge Centre are located

2. Arctic strategies, programmes and organisations

2.1 Norwegian strategies

The Norwegian Government's Arctic strategy is expressed in two recent White papers to the Parliament: "Melding til Stortinget: Svalbard (No. 32, 2015-2016)" and "Mennesker, muligheter, og norske interesser i Nord (No 9, 2020-2021)". The new [White paper on Svalbard](#) was published in May 2024, emphasizing that the most important areas for Norwegian activities and presence in Svalbard are research and education. A [strategy for research and higher education in Svalbard](#) was prepared in 2018, showing the Government's long-term investment in these activities to become the new pillars of the Svalbard community.

During the [Norwegian chairship](#) of the Arctic Council 2023-2025 one of the priority themes is "The Oceans". In this theme it is a priority for Norway develop "Arctic observation systems" which includes the central Arctic Ocean. Development of observing systems is stated in the research strategies of the Research Council of Norway, which are expressed in several documents. These include [Research and Innovation in the North](#) (2019), the [Norwegian Roadmap for research infrastructures](#) (2018), "[Havforskningstiåret](#)" (2020), the *Portfolio plans for Ocean, Climate and Polar research* (2022), and [Empowering ideas for a better world](#), the Research Council of Norway's strategy for 2020-2024.

In the report "[Blue Ocean, Green Future](#)", the Government's commitment to ocean and ocean industries is described, where the importance of the oceans for the Norwegian economy and society is highlighted. The ocean provides opportunities for growth and employment in areas such as energy production, seafood, medicines and transport. However, the world's oceans are also facing significant challenges, such as the loss of biodiversity, pollution, rising temperatures and acidification. One of the Government's most important tasks is to build a strong and sustainable ocean economy based on preserving clean and healthy oceans with well-functioning ecosystems, and enabling value creation through sustainable use. This will be essential for achieving the United Nations [Sustainable Development Goals](#), and important for overcoming current crises and preventing future crises.

Figure 2.1 Cover page of the documents "Havforskningstiåret" and "Blue Ocean, Green Future"

The Norwegian research strategy in the Arctic has strong focus on international collaboration, where participation in international organisations and programmes is fundamental for the collaboration. The main organisations of importance for Norway's observing activities in the Arctic are WMO and Eumetsat regarding meteorology and climate, Copernicus Marine monitoring and forecasting services, European Space Agency (ESA) regarding satellite observations, International Maritime Organisation (IMO) regarding shipping, International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) regarding fisheries management, several European programmes (section 2.2) and Arctic Council working groups (section 2.3).

2.2 European strategies and programmes

The EU's [updated Arctic Policy from 2021](#) aims to help preserve the Arctic as a region of peaceful cooperation, to slow the effects of climate change, and to support the sustainable development of Arctic regions to the benefit of Arctic communities, not least Indigenous Peoples, and future generations. The implementation of the EU's Arctic policy will help the Union to deliver the targets defined by the EU Green Deal and meet its geopolitical interests. The EU is a major funder and supporter of Polar science through its research and innovation framework programmes, and through its polar research policy, initiatives and actions. During the framework programmes Horizon 2020 (2014-2020) and Horizon Europe (2021-2027) EU has so far supported 139 Arctic projects with a total of 372 million €. In the [strategic plan](#) for Horizon Europe for 2025 – 2027 the EU has defined three key priorities: (i) the green transition, (ii) the digital transition, and (iii) a more resilient, competitive, inclusive and democratic Europe. This implies that research and innovation projects need to have impact on these priority areas.

From 2015 to 2020 the [EU-PolarNet](#) project developed and delivered a strategic framework and mechanisms to prioritise science and optimise the use of polar infrastructure as basis for polar research. In 2020 the project published a set of [white papers](#) giving the EU and national research agencies recommendations on research themes that are of high importance in the Polar Regions (Fig. 2.2). The recommendations were identified and formulated by a team of 50 experts from 16 countries in the following white papers:

1. The coupled polar climate system: global context, predictability and regional impacts
2. Footprints on changing polar ecosystems: processes, threats, responses and opportunities for future generations
3. Managing human impacts, resource use and conservation of the Polar regions
4. The road to the desired states of social-ecological systems in the Polar regions
5. Advancing operational informatics¹ for Polar regions

Figure 2.2 Coverpage of the EU PolarNet white papers from 2020

¹ Informatics studies on the representation, processing and communication of information in natural and engineered systems. It has computational, cognitive and social aspects.” (University of Edinburgh, School of Informatics 2017).

A follow-up project, [EU-Polarnet 2](#), running from 2020 to 2024, work continued to co-develop and advance European Polar research actions and to give evidence-based advice to policymaking processes. A major outcome of the project is the establishment of the European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO), which will follow up the EU-Polarnet work. EPCO will serve as a contact point between the European science community and the [European Commission](#) and other policy makers and relevant stakeholders. From January 2025, EPCO will be hosted by the [European Polar Board](#) (EPB), which is an independent organisation focused on major strategic priorities in the Arctic and Antarctic. A [recent white paper](#) gives recommendations to accelerate the development of a sustained and fully integrated Polar observing system (EU-Polarnet, 2024).

The [Copernicus programme](#) was established by EU in 2014 and is the world's largest Earth observation system using satellite as the main data source, producing global observations of our planet and its environment. Copernicus is part of the EU Space Programme in collaboration with Space agencies and other European agencies. Copernicus is served by a set of [dedicated satellites](#), also denoted the Sentinel families, developed by European Space Agency (Fig. 2.3) and contributing missions (existing commercial and public satellites). The Sentinel satellites are specifically designed to meet the needs of the Copernicus services and their users.

Figure 2.3 Illustration of the [Sentinel satellites from ESA](#)

Since the launch of Sentinel-1A in 2014, the European Union will launch a constellation of almost 20 more satellites into orbit before 2030. Vast amounts of global data from satellites and ground-based, airborne, and seaborne measurement systems provide information to help service providers, public authorities, and other international organisations to improve European citizens' quality of life and beyond. The information services provided are free and openly accessible to users.

In February 2020, the European Commission Directorate-General for Research and Innovation and the European Space Agency signed a cooperation agreement to jointly advance [Earth System Science](#) and its response to the global challenges that society is facing at the onset of this century. A key activity is to organise the [European Polar Science Week](#), where EU and ESA work together to identify and address the grand science challenges in polar research that may drive joint EC-ESA scientific activities in the coming years.

The [European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures](#) (ESFRI) was established in 2002 by representatives from the member states and associated members of the European Union to play a leading role in the development of pan-European research infrastructures (RI). The EU recognized the importance of excellent RIs to conduct leading research and ESFRI develops a [Roadmap](#) where RIs are selected and upgraded in a 10-20 year perspective (Fig. 2.5).

Figure 2.4 ESFRI logo

The ESFRI Roadmap 2021 is the sixth edition of the document, which has been influencing the European and national RIs strategies, policies and funding since 2006. The Roadmap identifies European investment priorities in RIs and provides directions for their further development. The implementation of the Roadmap is funded by national contributions. Since 2016 ESFRI has introduced the Landscape Analysis in its Roadmaps, providing an overview of the RI ecosystem, identifying key RIs and their global positioning. The Landscape Analysis has progressively evolved (2018, 2021) towards a more comprehensive and strategic document, now including trend analysis and the first examples of RIs services and their impacts in specific areas. The most [recent Landscape Analysis](#) was published in May 2024.

Figure 2.5. Lifecycle approach of a research infrastructures under ESFRI (ESFRI 2021).

The Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observation System (SIOS) was on the ESFRI Roadmap from 2009 to 2018. SIOS is an international observing system for long-term measurements in and around the Norwegian archipelago of Svalbard addressing Earth System Science questions. From 2018 SIOS has been in the operational phase with the name [Svalbard Knowledge Centre](#), with funding from the Research Council of Norway and contribution from the member institutions. At present several Norwegian RI projects are on the 2021 Roadmap, and a few of them have activities in the Arctic. These include EISCAT, ACTRIS, and ICOS with observing stations in Svalbard. To become a new RI on the Roadmap ESFRI organizes open calls for proposals and select new RIs based on reviews and strict eligibility criteria. The selected RI’s follow a lifecycle of six phases as shown in Fig. 2.5.

2.3 The Arctic Council

The Arctic Council is the leading intergovernmental forum promoting cooperation, coordination and interaction among the eight Arctic States (Canada, Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, Russian Federation, Sweden and the United States of America), Arctic indigenous communities and other Arctic inhabitants on common Arctic issues, in particular on issues of sustainable development and environmental protection in the Arctic. The Council's activities are primarily conducted in six [Working Groups](#) (Fig. 2.6) and one stand-alone [Expert Group](#) that cover a broad field of subjects, from climate change to emergency response, from mental health to sustainable development. The

Council also has six Indigenous Peoples’ organisations as members and some non-Arctic states, along with inter-governmental, inter-parliamentary, global, regional and non-governmental organizations as observers (<https://arctic-council.org>).

Figure 2.6. The Arctic Council Working groups and Indigenous Peoples’ organisations

The [Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks](#) (SAON) is a joint initiative of the Arctic Council and the International Arctic Science Committee that aims to strengthen multinational engagement in pan-Arctic observing. The SAON process was established in 2011 at the Seventh Ministerial Meeting of the Arctic Council (AC) via the Nuuk Declaration. SAON has adopted a [10-year strategy](#) for 2018-2028 for addressing current and future Arctic observing needs. In this strategy the Arctic Indigenous Peoples’s observing priorities and needs are central where the concept of shared Arctic variables (SAVs) has been introduced ([Bradley et al. 2023](#)).

The Arctic Council adopted in 2021 a [strategic plan for the next 10 years](#). The plan consists of six strategic goals (Table 2.1) and a number of strategic actions for each goal. The vision is that by 2030 the “Arctic will remain a region of peace, stability and constructive cooperation, that is a vibrant, prosperous, sustainable and secure home for all its inhabitants, including Indigenous Peoples, and where their rights and wellbeing are respected”

Table 2.1 Strategic goals
Goal 1 – Arctic Climate
Goal 2 – Healthy and Resilient Arctic Ecosystems
Goal 3 – Healthy Arctic Marine Environment
Goal 4 – Sustainable Social Development
Goal 5 - Sustainable Economic Development
Goal 6 – Knowledge and Communication
Goal 7 – Stronger Arctic Council

In 2017 the eight Arctic governments signed the [Agreement on Enhancing International Arctic Scientific Cooperation](#) (sometimes colloquially referred to as the Arctic Science Agreement). The Agreement facilitates access by scientists of the eight Arctic governments to Arctic areas that each government has identified, including entry and exit of persons, equipment, and materials; access to research infrastructure and facilities; and access to data. The Agreement also calls for the parties to promote education, career development and training opportunities, and encourages activities associated with traditional and local knowledge.

The [Arctic Economic Council](#) (AEC) is an independent organization that facilitates Arctic business-to-business activities and responsible economic development through the sharing of best practices. AEC was created by the Arctic Council during the 2013-2015 Canadian chairmanship. The members are corporations, indigenous groups and partnerships across the Arctic that have an economic interest in the region (Fig. 2.7). The goal is to facilitate responsible business and economic development of the Arctic and its communities. AEC will share and advocate for best practices, technological solutions, and standards. AEC has identified the main business areas of important in the Arctic (Table 2.2).

Table 2.2 Business areas for the AEC

- (1) Maritime transportation
- (2) Communications and IT
- (3) Aviation
- (4) Energy, including oil, gas and renewable sources
- (5) Mining
- (6) Tourism
- (7) Blue economy and
- (8) Human Resources Investments and capacity building.

Figure 2.7. Logo of Arctic Economic Council and map of countries with member organisations

SIX BASIC PRINCIPLES FOR INVESTORS TO FOLLOW

- 1 | Build Resilient Societies Through Economic Development
- 2 | Respect and Include Local Communities and Indigenous Peoples
- 3 | Pursue Measures to Protect the Environment of the Arctic
- 4 | Practice Responsible and Transparent Business Methods
- 5 | Consult and Integrate Science and Traditional Ecological Knowledge
- 6 | Strengthen Pan-Arctic Collaboration and Sharing of Best Practices

Figure 2.8. Guidelines for investors in the Arctic

A report titled [“Sustainable Investment Opportunities in the Arctic”](#) has been made by a group of experts from the Arctic region. The report includes business cases of large companies as well as SMEs from different economic sectors such as mining, tourism, bioeconomy, energy, technology, and infrastructure. AEC has also produced an [Arctic Investment Protocol](#) with guidelines for responsible development in the Arctic (Fig. 2.8).

2.4 Environmental protection, shipping and safety at sea

An important treaty to protect the marine environment in the European part of the Arctic Ocean is the [Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic](#) (the ‘OSPAR Convention’). The regions covered by OSPAR are shown in Fig. 2.9. The convention covers pollution prevention, assessment, research, compliance and regional cooperation. It was signed by 15 European countries and the European Commission in 1992 and entered into force in 1998. The convention regulates European standards on [marine biodiversity](#), [eutrophication](#), the release of [hazardous](#) and [radioactive](#) substances into the seas, the [offshore oil and gas industry](#) and baseline monitoring of environmental conditions. Programmes and measures relating to fisheries management in the north east Atlantic and [North Sea](#) are currently coordinated by the [International Council for the Exploration of the Sea](#) (ICES). The strategic and operational objectives for OSPAR for the decade 2020-2030 is formulated in the [North-East Atlantic Environment Strategy \(NEAES\) 2030](#), where the guiding principles are (1) Ecosystem approach, (2) Precautionary principle, (3) Polluter Pays principle, (4) Best Available Techniques and Best Environmental Practices.

Figure 2.9 Left: A map of the OSPAR Maritime Area, denoting sub-regions I to V, as defined by the OSPAR convention. Ecosystem Accounting was performed by seafloor type (A3 – A6), according to EUNIS classifications; Right: Map of OSPAR Marine protected areas (<https://oap.ospar.org/eng/>).

Ship traffic is a major contributor to the impact on the marine environment. In the Arctic the ship traffic is growing as a result of decrease of sea ice combined with exploitation of oil, gas, and other natural resources. This is of considerable concern which is addressed in IMO’s [Polar Code](#), in PAME’s work, by tourist organisations such as [AECO](#) and others involved in protecting the Arctic marine environment. As illustrated in Fig. 2.10 the main impact comes from:

- emission from the fuel
- oil spills
- marine litter incl. plastics
- disturbance of wildlife
- invasive species
- noise pollution

The Arctic Council’s working group **Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment (PAME)** is monitoring and analysing ship traffic data based on [AIS data from satellites and coastal stations](#). The AIS data provides useful statistics on ship traffic within the Polar Code area, showing that the highest ship traffic in the Arctic is found in the Barents Sea and around Svalbard, in the Northern Sea Route along the Russian coast (Fig. 2.11). The ship traffic is caused by fishing vessels, tourist ships, transport to and from the oil and gas fields in Russia, and bulk vessels in Davis Strait / Baffin Bay and many other types of transport.

Figure 2.10 The main types of environmental impacts from shipping (Qi et al.,2024)

Figure 2.11. Ship traffic data within the Polar Code area from the Arctic Shipping Status Report provided by PAME’s [Arctic Ship Traffic Data](#) service. Left: The total distance sailed by all vessels per year, showing that the traffic has doubled from 2013 to 2023. The AIS data also shows that the total number of unique vessels sailing in the Arctic has increased from 1298 in 2013 to 1782 in 2023. Right: Ship tracks in September 2019 for different types of vessels.

The need for better search and rescue (SAR) infrastructure and capabilities in the Arctic is well documented because of increased ship traffic and other human activities. The SAR infrastructure is complex in the Arctic due to vast distances, a harsh climate, communication challenges, and sparse population and limited SAR resources (Fig. 2.12). Furthermore, it is important to build up knowledge about risk and safety among people who travel, work or live in the regions. There is a number of research projects addressing risk and safety of maritime activities where SAR is a central component. The SAR operations in Norway are organized by the [Joint Rescue and Coordination Center](#), (JRCC), which has a wider range of resources to its disposal for quick, safe and effective SAR operations. JRCC is coordinating the first EU funded project on Arctic safety, [ARCSAR](#) (Arctic and North Atlantic Security and Emergency Preparedness Network) from 2018 to 2024. The factors that make safety more challenging in the Arctic compared to other places are the following:

- cold conditions and extreme weather conditions, leading to higher risk that people and equipment will not function
- remoteness, long distances and limited infrastructure implies that assistance in case of accidents will take much longer time
- climate change is stronger, leading to more extreme weather events and consequently more severe natural hazards

Figure 2.12. (a) Norwegian Coastguard icebreaker KV Svalbard is the most important vessel for search and rescue operations in the Norwegian sector of the Arctic; (b) Map of the Search and Rescue (SAR) area where Norway has responsibility according to the [agreement](#) signed in 2011 by the Arctic Council ministers (black line). The thin red lines show Norway's EEZ areas.

Svalbard's strategic location with communication, infrastructure and other resources is very important for development of safety and SAR services. In this effort shipping operators, search and rescue agencies, NGOs and academia are enhancing their efforts to safe and sustainable shipping in Arctic waters. The [Arctic Safety Centre](#) at UNIS has been mentioned as a unique establishment to provide research, education and training in Arctic safety for the local community, scientists, students, tourists and others operators. The centre has a leading role in developing safety standards for outdoor activities in Svalbard, while the Governor provides information on rules and regulations.

2.5 Arctic Science Ministerial

In 2016 president Obama initiated the [first Arctic Science Ministerial](#) (ASM) in Washington DC, when Arctic science was brought to a higher political level. More than 25 countries, the European Union and various organisations gathered at the ASM in 2016. Follow up events were held 2018 and 2021 to strengthen efforts and collaboration in Arctic research. The third ASM in 2021 (Fig. 2.13) had “Knowledge for a sustainable Arctic” as the overarching theme. The main outcome of [ASM3](#) was a Joint Statement to be signed by the Ministers of 27 participating countries and the EU proposing actions in the four priority areas:

- Observe - Observing networks; Data sharing –towards implementation
- Understand - Enhance understanding and prediction capability on Arctic environmental and social systems and its global impact
- Respond - Sustainable development; Evaluation of vulnerability and resilience; Application of knowledge
- Strengthen - Capacity building; Education; Networking; Resilience –prepare the next generation

2.6 UN Decade of Ocean Science

The UN Decade of Ocean Science from 2021 to 2030 ([the Ocean Decade](#)) is a global endeavor to create a significant collaborative momentum for ocean-related sustainable development and science (Fig. 2.14). The Ocean Decade has formulated a number of goals which are defined as the following societal outcomes, listed in Table 2.3.

Table 2.3 Ocean Decade goals

- A clean ocean where sources of pollution are identified, reduced or removed
- A healthy and resilient ocean where marine ecosystems are understood, safeguarded and managed
- A productive ocean supporting sustainable food supply and a sustainable ocean economy
- A predicted ocean where society understands and can respond to changing ocean conditions
- A safe ocean where life and livelihoods and their integrity are protected from ocean-related hazards
- An accessible ocean with open and equitable access to data, information and technology and innovation
- An inspiring and engaging ocean where society understands and values the ocean in relation to human wellbeing and sustainable development, and cultural integrity of Indigenous peoples reliant on the ocean and coastal seas.

The importance of the oceans has been raised to high political level by the G7 countries through establishing the G7 FSOI: [Future of the Seas and Ocean Initiative](#) (Fig. 2.15). The initiative offers a mechanism to address the challenge of strengthening and sustaining ocean observations through the coordinated actions of the 7 leading nations in ocean observing plus the EU, who together fund more than half of global ocean observations. The FSOI working group organizes workshops with representatives from government agencies and ministries across the G7 and the European Commission and marine scientists to enhance the global ocean observing system. In a recent workshop two new emerging issues were discussed: ‘**Arctic Ocean Observing**’ and ‘**Marine Research Infrastructures Integration and Harmonization**’.

Figure 2.15. The G7 FSOI logo

Another policy initiative is the High Level Panel for A Sustainable Ocean Economy ([The Ocean Panel](#)), which was established in 2018, where 18 countries representing 50 % of the world’s coastline and 45 % of the global EEZ are members. The Panel works with government, business, financial institutions, the scientific community and the civil society to find solutions for a sustainable ocean economy. The panel has commissioned research with input from 350 experts in 54 countries, resulting in comprehensive assessment of ocean science and knowledge with significant policy relevance. The results are published in a number of blue papers, guides and reports available on the website.

The [Arctic Action Plan](#) under the United Nations’ Ocean Decade is a regional plan presenting the first steps of challenges to be addressed in the Arctic regions. The plan was kicked-off in 2021 and is expected to be updated throughout the Decade while it addresses several Sustainable Development Goals (e.g. SDG 14 “Life below water” and 13 “Climate action”). The Arctic Plan has been structured around three types of challenges:

Research challenges – core scientific areas that should be advanced to enable the production of transformative ocean science solutions. A central element is to implement and operate ocean observing systems providing spatial and temporal information on bathymetry, oceanographic conditions, documenting geodiversity and biodiversity, disaster and pollution risks, provisioning of ecosystem services and their value to support evidence-based decision making.

Organizational challenges – devising effective strategies to provide and support efficient coordination, coherence, funding, infrastructure, data management and public support to activities in the regions throughout the year

Uptake challenges – options for enhancing and accelerating the societal utilisation and benefits of ocean science solutions in the Arctic regions and beyond.

To follow up the Arctic Action Plan, a number of international programmes, initiatives and organisations will address the different Arctic challenges. In particular, the [International Arctic Science Committee \(IASC\)](#), including the International Conference on Arctic Research Planning (ICARP IV) and the International Polar Year 2032-33, will play a central role in the process of planning and implementing actions in the Arctic. In Norway the Research Council has proposed a number of actions for the Ocean Decade (“Havforskningstiåret”) where the research and management of the Arctic Ocean is one of the 10 priorities.

2.7 IASC and the ICARP IV Process (2022-2026)

The International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) in cooperation with many partners worldwide, is coordinating a multi-year planning process for the [Fourth International Conference on Arctic Research Planning \(ICARP IV\)](#) lasting from 2022 until 2026 (Fig. 2.16). ICARP conferences are organized once per decade, the previous ones were in 1995, 2005 and 2015. The process engages Arctic researchers, Indigenous Peoples, policy makers, residents and stakeholders from around the world to collegially discuss the state of Arctic science and plan Arctic research in the next 10 years. The main event is the ICARP IV Summit, organized together with the Arctic Science Summit Week in Boulder, Colorado, USA from 20-28 March 2025. The event will include a number of business and community meetings which will contribute to the research priorities teams listed in Table 2.4.

Fig. 2.16. Diagram of the ICARP IV process 2022-2026 (<https://icarp.iasc.info/>)

Table 2.4 ICARP IV research priority teams

- 1: The Role of the Arctic in the Global System
- 2: Observing, Reconstructing, and Predicting Future Climate Dynamics and Ecosystem Responses
- 3: Understanding the Vulnerability and Resilience of Arctic Environments and Societies and Supporting Sustainable Development
- 4: Arctic Research Cooperation and Diplomacy
- 5: Co-Production and Indigenous-led methodologies
- 6: Preparing present and future generations through Education, Outreach, Communication, Capacity Building, and Networking
- 7: Technology, Infrastructure, Logistics, and Services

Part of the ICARP IV process is to support the planning of the International Polar Year 2032-33 (next section).

2.8 International Polar Year 2032-33

Planning of the 5th International Polar Year (IPY) 2032-33 has started under leadership of IASC and SCAR (Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research). The motivation is stated on the IASC website as follows:

The next decade “...is a critical decade for people and the planet. Extreme weather, rising temperatures, rising sea levels, and devastating events such as droughts, floods, wildfires, marine warming, ocean acidification, and record lows in sea ice extent are becoming ever more prevalent, affecting ecosystems, economies, and human wellbeing around the world. Many changes are taking shape faster than previously predicted, and as the IPCC 6th Assessment Report made clear, many of the most serious consequences are linked to unprecedented changes in the Arctic and Antarctic. The urgency of understanding the consequences of such rapid change in the polar regions for global climate, biodiversity and human societies is now clear and has never been greater.”

During the IPY research on polar and global issues will be intensified to produce new knowledge about the Arctic and Antarctic needed for evidence-based policies and decision-making. It will follow up the [4th IPY \(2007-2008\)](#), where thousands of polar scientists and others study the changes of the cryosphere, oceans, atmosphere, landscapes and people living in the polar regions. It was emphasized that the changes in the polar regions have global impact and need to be communicated to the society.

In the initial [concept note for IPY 2032-22](#), published by IASC in October 2023 (Fig. 2.17), the principles of IPY 2032-33 are outlined, where the general activities will include:

- Allow researchers and knowledge holders to capitalise on the outcomes of previous IPYs by expanding integrated and coordinated observations of accelerating changes, and long-term monitoring required to understand current conditions and inform predictions of future states;
- Provide a comprehensive assessment of the operation and evolution of polar ecosystems enabling a more holistic understanding of the Earth’s interconnected systems and climate change trajectory, as well as supporting practical global and local adaptation solutions.
- Build on the methodological, technological, and epistemological advancements of the 4th IPY, including major shifts toward working across knowledge systems;
- Achieve a step-change in transdisciplinary polar research through meaningful integration of natural sciences, social sciences, humanities research, and Indigenous knowledge systems.

Fig. 2.17. Front page of the IPY 2032-33 concept note

3 Requirements for Arctic Ocean Observing Systems

3.1 The framework for ocean observing

The Arctic region is exposed to significant environmental changes including the overall thinning and melting of sea ice, which opens up new areas for resource exploitation and ship traffic. The increased human activities will put more pressure on the Arctic Ocean environment including the underwater acoustic environment. While polar orbiting satellites collect large amounts of data from the ocean surface including sea ice (e.g. the Sentinel programme under Copernicus), there are huge gaps in the data coverage under the sea ice. The Arctic Ocean is among the least observed oceans in the world, and there is practically no long-term observing infrastructure for the central Arctic Ocean. Around 70 % of the ocean data collected in the Arctic are funded by time-limited research programs. It is therefore important to establish funding mechanisms for long-term in situ observations in the Arctic Ocean (Ludwigsen et al. 2018).

There is a broad range of climate and environmental issues as well as human activities that need ocean observation, both globally and in the Arctic. The societal benefit areas for Arctic observing were defined in the *International Arctic Observations Assessment Framework* document published by IDA-STPI (2017) for SAON (Fig. 3.1) and were further explored in the *Impact assessment study on societal benefits of Arctic observing systems*, published by JRC (Dobricic et al., 2018).

Societal Benefits Area
1. Disaster Preparedness
2. Environmental Quality
3. Food Security
4. Fundamental Understanding of Arctic Systems
5. Human Health
6. Infrastructure and Operations
7. Marine and Coastal Ecosystems and Processes
8. Natural Resource
9. Resilient Communities
10. Sociocultural Services
11. Terrestrial and Freshwater Ecosystems and Processes
12. Weather and Climate

Figure 3.1 Cover page of the SAON report (left) and the list of Societal Benefit Areas according to SAON

The requirements for ocean observing systems are expressed in a suite of policy documents, conventions, treaties, and other agreements (i.e. climate, environment, biodiversity, sustaining ecosystem services, improving the livelihoods of indigenous and local communities, and support to maritime safety). The requirements are analyzed for the different scientific disciplines and application

areas. The requirements are then specified in terms of which variable to observe, which technologies to be applied, the spatiotemporal resolution, timeliness and quality of the observations and derived data products. Finally, there are requirements for dissemination and management of data to ensure that data products are accessible and can be exploited by users.

The [Global Ocean Observing System](#) (GOOS) is the overarching organization for ocean observations established in 1991² with head office at UNESCO in Paris. In the [2030 Strategy of GOOS](#) the societal need for ocean information is described and illustrated in Fig. 3.2. The four components of an integrated ocean observing system are (1) Observations, (2) Data Management, (3) Analysis and Models, and (4) Applications.

Figure 3.2. Illustration of the integrated global ocean observing system and its applications (adapted from GOOS 2030).

² GOOS is co-sponsored by Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) under UNESCO World Meteorological Organisation (WMO,) United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and the Intenational Science Council (ISC.)
30 September 2024

GOOS has defined a set of Essential Ocean Variables (EOV) representing global standards for the data to be collected to support the societal benefit areas. The EOVs provide data on ocean circulation and distribution of and transport of heat, salt and other water properties listed in Fig. 3.3. When new observing technologies become available they can be employed to continue collection of consistent data sets. A key issue is the feasibility of the observing technology. Before an observing system can be implemented, the feasibility should be assessed technically, politically and economically. The EOVs are the bases for ocean science disciplines and operational ocean services. Now there is particular focus on observing climate change through sea ice decline, temperature increase and changes in marine ecosystems, sea level rise and the societal consequences of these changes. Topics related to climate change are conservation of marine ecosystems, management of natural resources, living conditions for Indigenous People and local communities. In the Arctic the decline of sea ice opens up for shipping in new areas providing opportunities for industry and economic development.

Physics	Biochemistry	Biology and Ecosystems
Sea state Ocean surface stress Sea ice Sea surface height Sea surface temperature Subsurface temperature Surface currents Subsurface currents Sea surface salinity Subsurface salinity Ocean surface heat flux Ocean bottom pressure Turbulent diapycnal fluxes (*pilot)	Oxygen Nutrients Inorganic carbon Transient tracers Particulate matter Nitrous oxide Stable carbon isotopes Dissolved organic carbon	Phytoplankton biomass and diversity Zooplankton biomass and diversity Fish abundance and distribution Marine turtles, birds, mammals abundance and distribution Hard coral cover and composition Seagrass cover and composition Macroalgal canopy cover and composition Mangrove cover and composition Microbe biomass and diversity (*pilot) Invertebrate abundance and distribution (*pilot)
Cross-disciplinary (including human impact)		
	Ocean colour Marine debris (*pilot)	Ocean sound

Figure 3.3. List of the Essential Ocean Variables. Orange colour indicate the official variable, while black indicate pilot variables ([GOOS website](#)).

A [Framework for Ocean Observing](#) (FOO, 2012) was prepared after the OceanObs’09 conference to guide the establishment of ocean observing systems. The FOO is organised around the EOVs and therefore includes ocean physics, biogeochemistry, and ocean biology and ecosystems. The concept of the FOO is illustrated by three main components as illustrated in Fig. 3.4.

The input is represented by the requirements defined by the scientific disciplines and the societal issues (e.g. climate monitoring, ecosystem management, natural hazard warning). The processes include the observing activities using platforms and sensors to collect the data described by the requirements. The third component is the outputs, which are data products and information used in scientific work, services for society and in decision making. Finally, there is a feedback loop back to the requirements to be updated and improve the observing systems so they are relevant for the societal issues that help to formulated the requirements.

Figure 3.4. Left: A highly simplified representation for a basic system. Right: Structure of the Framework for Ocean Observing, showing how different observing systems feeds into data products and the feedback loop to requirements. The observing systems listed are examples (FOO, 2012).

The FOO can be described as a circular process called the “Ocean observing value chain” (Pearlman et al., 2019) illustrated in Fig. 3.5. The value chain is a set of activities in each of the six boxes performed by one or more communities to create and distribute ocean data products or services.

Figure 3.5. Ocean observing value chain from requirements to societal benefits (Pearlman et al., 2019).

The value chain is evaluated and updated for each EOV in response to new requirements and when new scientific methods, new data and improved services are implemented. The evaluation includes both the scientific -technical aspects and the social dimension of ocean observing. The social dimension deals with cooperation, trust, ethics and other human aspects that need to be addressed in order for the value chain be effective for the societal benefit areas.

In developing Ocean Observing for specific EOVs, the FOO uses the term “readiness level” where the readiness of requirements, observation elements and data and information products are assessed. In order to include a new observation of an EOV into the global ocean observing system, each of the steps in the value chain need to mature, following the three readiness levels described in Fig. 3.6

Figure 3.6. Framework Processes and Readiness Levels. Requirements, Observations, and Data & Information products move through readiness levels within the Framework. Each component will experience rigorous review, vetting, and approval by the community before reaching the highest level of readiness. This process will allow for innovation while protecting the system from inadequate or duplicative solutions (FOO, 2012).

The role of different actors involved in ocean observing can be divided into three functional groups: oversight groups, EOV expert teams, and implementation communities. The basic functions of each group are described in Table 3.2. Actors in all groups are involved as the community assesses the needs for sustaining or improving observations of each EOV, and linking observations to societal drivers, following the value chain circle in Fig. 3.5.

The FOO, which is based on broad community collaboration, will improve communications and data sharing across the community; result in faster and better coordinated information to support both research and societal needs; contribute to capacity building and enhancement of ocean observations in developing countries; increase confidence and support among sponsoring and funding entities; and foster innovation and scientific discovery (Fisher, 2013).

Table 3.2. The functional groups in FOO

Functional groups	Primary activities
Oversight and coordination	Groups that have as their primary purpose to review the development of information requirements in response to societal needs align ocean observing activities accordingly. These groups will also bring partners together to coordinate and align with their activities. They are the key linkages to stakeholders outside of the Framework.
Expert EOV Reviews	Groups that align to evaluate best-practices, and to design and assess the feasibility of building and managing the ongoing measurements required to study and understand the EOVs. Through evaluation of the needs for standardization and innovation along with readiness levels they then develop an EOV implementation strategy.
EOV implementation	These groups are the basic unit and core of the observing system. They are communities that form around common challenges on a type of observing platform, steering the development of particular networks. They can also be communities that focus on data management challenges, or the production of integrated data products focused on a particular EOV. They can also have a regional focus.

3.2 Stakeholders and users of Arctic Ocean observing systems

There is a large group of stakeholders who need information about Arctic research and environmental status, and different human activities in the region. Stakeholders are people and organisations with responsibilities for activities or are affected by any issues within the Societal Benefit Areas in the Arctic (Fig. 3.7). The stakeholders form a wide variety of public and private sectors, which can broadly be divided into:

- (1) Scientists who use data from the observing systems in research and education
- (2) Public sector bodies, with national or international mandates to deliver public services, carry out assessments and have responsibilities within different societal sectors
- (3) Private sector, including fisheries, aquaculture, oil and gas, wind energy, tourism, transport, technology providers, insurance, and other commercial service providers.
- (4) Non-governmental organisations
- (5) Indigenous People and local communities
- (6) International bodies, organisations and networks
- (7) Media

Fig. 3.7. List of Arctic stakeholder according to INTAROS (Sandven et al., 2022)

The stakeholders who are direct users of data from the Arctic Ocean observing systems are scientists and operational monitoring and forecasting services. They are also the main users and operators of the observing systems, where companies develop the sensors and platforms for data collection. The observing systems consists of polar orbiting satellites, airborne systems, and a number of in situ systems deployed by vessels in the ocean, on the seafloor, on the sea ice and along the coasts. In the polar regions satellites are the main producers of sea ice and ocean data every data, especially from the Sentinel satellites that deliver data in near real-time as part of the Copernicus programme. The collection of in situ data is much more limited because of logistically constraints.

The needs and requirements for Arctic observations are defined in collaboration between scientists, service providers and other stakeholders. The requirements are updated through an iterative process taking into account new developments in technology, essential variables, and new societal needs. The observing systems are therefore developed, scaled and adapted to a wide variety of stakeholders needs. The engagement of users and stakeholders in developing ocean observing systems can be described by the following seven points and the circular process shown in Fig. 3.8.

Figure 3.8. The steps required for successful user engagement (Source: U.S. IOOS Summit report) published in 2013 by Interagency Ocean Observation Committee for development of an Integrated Ocean Observing System (www.iooc.us). Each of the steps present challenges, many of them related to communication and coordination.

1. Users and stakeholders are identified and engaged in formulating the needs for ocean observations, data products, and services within their domain.
2. Scientists, service providers and users prioritize what data should be provided, taking into account scientific quality, technical feasibility and costs of different observing systems

3. The requirements for data according to priority are specified in dialogue between users, scientist and service providers
4. Development and implementation of the observing systems to produce the required data products and services
5. Outreach activities where the data products and services are disseminated and promoted to a wider community of users
6. Obtain feedback from the users, assess the data products and services, while continuing the operation of the observing system.
7. Provide training and education of the personnel involved in the different parts of the value chain

The users of ocean observations are people who work with ocean data as part of their professional job in all of the four components of the observing system. These are mostly scientists, service providers, operational agencies and companies conducting specific tasks which require data from the ocean. An overview of the main user groups are presented in Table 3.3.

Table 3.3 Table of major user groups

User group	Comments
Scientists	Scientists who work in the field to collect, analyse and publish data in oceanography, sea ice, meteorology, marine biology, biogeochemistry, marine geology, seismology, acoustics
	Scientists using data in developing models and data assimilation methods for use in research and operational services
	Network of scientists working with climate assessments, marine ecosystem and resource assessments and policy recommendations for specific regions (AMAP, OSPAR) and on global scale (IPCC)
Service providers	Ocean, weather and sea ice monitoring and forecasting services (national agencies, Copernicus marine services, commercial services)
	Monitoring of biodiversity, marine ecosystems, eutrophication, acidification and pollution (including radioactive substances)
	Monitoring of natural hazards (earthquakes, tsunamis, extreme flooding, radioactive substances)
Governmental agencies	Agencies and authorities using results from scientists and service providers in management, regulations and policy making (coastal administration, marine authority, directorates)
	Operational entities using monitoring and forecasting services: Vessel traffic control, pilots, ports, Search and Rescue, Coastguard, Navy
Ocean industry	Companies using monitoring and forecasting services include shipping and sea transport, offshore oil and gas, subsea companies, fisheries, aquaculture and various subcontractors. Companies in oil and gas production and aquaculture are also collectors of environmental data to be reported to the governmental agencies as part of their license to operate.
Others	Tourists and tourist operators
	NGOs
	Indigenous People, local communities and municipalities
	Media

Users and stakeholders within fisheries, aquaculture, marine transport, tourism, renewable energies, conservation, as well as climate, weather and ocean forecasting services need relevant, up-to-date, and integrated information to make knowledge-based decisions. The required products and services can range from high-level information to support policymaking, and management decisions to provision of information of sea ice, currents, and waves to ships. Identification of user requirements is not straightforward because of changing political priorities, new concerns among the stakeholders and new technologies which can advance the observing capabilities. Most stakeholders are not directly users of the data from the observing systems. They are usually interested in information derived from the data products or services in order to support one or more of the Societal Benefit Areas (SBAs). Those providing observations and synthesizing data should have dialogue with the stakeholders to capture their requirements. The stakeholders need to understand what observations are feasible to obtain in light of technological limitations and cost.

The connections between individual observing systems, the measured variables and provision of services addressing specific SBAs can be illustrated through data value chain as shown in Figure 3.9. The steps in the chain are described for sea ice forecasting service, where each step includes research activities to ensure that the services for the SBAs are science-based. In the Arctic the collection in situ data, as part of the observing systems, is often the bottleneck because there are few relevant platforms and sensors to produce the required data. The collection of space data, however, is well-developed because the Sentinel satellites produce sea ice data every day which are used in the forecasting services.

From observations to useful information for societal benefit areas

Figure 3.9. Examples of data value chain for sea ice forecasting services. Each column of the diagram corresponds to a step in the chain, from data collection in the observing systems (to the right) up to the services for the benefit of society (on the left). The development of the data value chain requires collaboration between researchers and service providers.

3.3 Requirements for in situ observations

The requirements for ocean observations for climate research are defined by the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) in “[The 2022 GCOS ECV Requirements report](#)” (GCOS-245). The report specifies a number of Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) to be observed for atmosphere, ocean and terrestrial data. The ocean ECVs are presented in Fig. 3.9, showing that the list of variables is similar to the list of EOVs (Figure 3.2). The difference is that the ECVs are more specific regarding marine ecosystem variables, identified chemical compounds, and distinction between surface and subsurface variables. **This implies that in situ observations are needed for most of the ocean ECVs.** The ECVs are specified in terms of definition of variable, measurement unit, measurement accuracy and uncertainty, stability, horizontal and vertical resolution, timeliness and temporal resolution, standards and references.

Observations in the Arctic follow the general specification given by CGOS, but logistical and infrastructure constraints make it difficult to collect in situ data in the same way as in other lower latitude oceans. It is also a challenge to collect data with autonomous system which can operate year-round. In practice, many of the ECV can only be observed by human operations, collecting samples and analyzing them in the lab to retrieve the ECVs.

Therefore, it is a necessary to find a balance between what would be “nice to have” and what is feasible to achieve from a technical, logistical, and especially economical point of view. A gridded format with fixed horizontal and vertical distances between data points is feasible for satellite data and models but is not practice for in situ data. Instead in situ data should be collected in key locations which are important for processes or can be representative for a larger region. To select such key locations is also difficult since large parts of the Arctic Ocean is unexplored.

Ocean	
ECV	ECV Product 2022
Sea-Surface temperature	Sea-Surface temperature
Subsurface Temperature	Interior Temperature
Sea-Surface Salinity	Sea-Surface Salinity
Subsurface Salinity	Interior Salinity
Surface Currents	Surface Geostrophic Current
	Ekman Currents
Subsurface Currents	Vertical Mixing
Sea Level	Regional Mean Sea Level
	Global Mean Sea Level
Sea State	Wave Height
Surface Stress	Surface Stress
Ocean Surface Heat Flux	Radiative Heat Flux
	Sensible Heat Flux
	Latent Heat Flux
Sea Ice	Sea Ice Concentration
	Sea Ice Thickness
	Sea Ice Drift
	Sea Ice Age
	Sea Ice Surface Temperature (IST)
	Sea ice Surface Albedo
	Snow Depth on Sea Ice
Oxygen	Dissolved Oxygen Concentration
Nutrients	Silicate
	Phosphate
	Nitrate
Ocean Inorganic Carbon	Total Alkalinity (TA)
	Dissolved Inorganic Carbon (DIC)
	pCO ₂
Transient Tracers	¹⁴ C
	SF ₆
	CFC-11
	CFC-12
Ocean nitrous oxide N ₂ O	Interior Ocean Nitrous Oxide N ₂ O
	N ₂ O Air-Sea Flux
Ocean Colour	Water Leaving Radiance
	Chlorophyll-a concentration
Plankton	Zooplankton Diversity
	Zooplankton Biomass
	Phytoplankton Diversity
	Phytoplankton Biomass
Marine Habitat Properties	Mangrove Cover and Composition
	Seagrass Cover (areal extent)
	Macroalgal Canopy Cover and Composition
	Hard coral cover and composition

Figure 3.9 List of Essential Climate Variables for the ocean provided by GCOS-245.

Another aspect is to distinguish between the requirements for an observing system optimised for the whole Arctic serving the global monitoring systems and the requirements for regional systems which serve national priorities as well international commitments. The location of the observing systems are usually based on the scientific topics to be studied combined with requirements for monitoring and forecasting services (e.g. weather forecasting, flooding and other natural hazards, fisheries management). In the end it is a matter of what is practical and cost-beneficial to implement.

In situ data provide the basis for:

- Documentation of the present state of the oceans, including physical, biological and chemical environment
- Analysis of ocean processes with seasonal, annual and decadal changes,
- Interpretation of satellite observations and validation of satellite-retrieved variables
- Validation of ocean models, data assimilation in models and support to monitoring and forecasting services

In the next section the methods for collecting in situ data in polar water is summarized

3.4 Observing platforms for use in the Arctic

On global scale there are a number of in situ observing systems, also called observing networks, which are based on specific platform types and organized as international programs. These include Argo, OceanSITES, DBCP (Data Buoy Cooperation Panel), SOT (Ship Observations Team), GO-SHIP, GLOSS (Global Sea Level Observing System) and OceanGlider. The programs are the major contributors the GOOS and the data delivery from each of them are organized under [OceanOPS](#), a portal tracking over 100.000 observations per day. OceanOPS provides a dashboard where all the observations can be found. A subset of the dashboard map, covering the Arctic and the North Atlantic, is shown in Fig. 3.10.

Figure 3.10. (a) Subset of the global map on the OceanOPS Dashboard as of 24 September 2024, showing all the observing networks under OceanOPS which are active on that date. In addition, there are unknown number of observations taken from research campaigns that do not necessarily report to OceanOPS. The red lines are observations along ship tracks obtained regularly and reported to the ship-based measurement programs shown in (b).

In the Arctic Ocean there much fewer observing platforms than in the North Atlantic and the Nordic Seas. The most common are the Polar Buoys under DBCP, which are deployed on ice and collect data on air pressure, temperature and GPS for accurate position and ice drift. There are also a number of Argo floats, mainly located around margins of the Arctic Ocean which is mostly ice-free in the summer months. There is very little oceanographic data from the ice-covered part of the Arctic Ocean reported in OceanOPS.

So what platforms are applicable to collect oceanographic data in the ice-covered Arctic Ocean ? In D2: “Report from the workshops in Tromsø and Stavanger”, the most important ocean observing systems for the ice-covered areas are described. Bottom-anchored moorings equipped with instrumentation from bottom to near-surface is the standard method for year-round and long-term observations, giving the temporal variability at fixed locations. In addition, ship-based CTD and water sample sections are needed to obtain 2-D and 3-D sampling of the ocean. The ship-based observations from icebreakers are seasonally biased because more data is collected in the summer months compared to the winter months. Regions with heavy ice are under-sampled because access to the areas is limited, except for the strongest icebreakers. Drifting buoys, deployed ice floes with instruments to observe atmosphere, sea ice and ocean, can in principle cover the whole ice-covered ocean. The International Arctic Buoy Program ([IABP](#)) coordinates and operates a number of different ice buoys (between 100 and 200) provided by institutions in North America and Europe. Most of them observe basic meteorological variables and sea ice drift. Some of them are contributors to the DBCP (Polar Buoys in Fig. 3.10) and stream the data into OceanOPS.

One type of ice buoys is the [Ice Mass Balance Buoys](#) (IMB), which measure ice thickness and snow thickness. Another type are the ocean buoys which have a string suspended below the ice with fixed depth or profiling instruments collecting ocean data to about 800 m for the ITP. The ITP drifting ocean buoys are developed and operated by WHOI. Typically 20 – 30 are in operation at any given time, and they are mostly deployed in the western hemisphere, where they can operate for several years (Fig. 3.11). Some of them are caught in the Transpolar Drift and move with the currents through the Fram Strait. These ocean buoys, as well as the other ice buoys, transmit data via satellite in near realtime to the users. When the ice buoys enter open water they continue to transmit data and can be recovered as long as they send position data. The ITP and TOP data are distributed by WHOI from the [ITP website](#).

Figure 3.11. Map of active ocean buoys as of 24 September 2024, providing profiling data down to 800 m for the ITPs (green dots) and 200 m for the TOPs (pink points). The data are available in near realtime from the ITP website (<https://www2.whoi.edu/site/itp/data/>)

Other platforms such as Argo floats, gliders, saildrones and seafloor observatories are evolving as important components of the global observing system, but in ice-covered areas they have limited capability to operate. Argo floats can operate under ice, but cannot reach the surface before it is in open water. At present some floats operate in the margins of the Arctic Ocean, which is ice-free in the summer. Several studies have described the gaps in ocean observations in the Arctic and pointed out the requirements and formulated recommendations on how to improve ocean monitoring and prediction (e.g. Smith et al., 2019, Whitt et al., 2020). Further elaboration of the topic will be presented in the follow-up report D4: “Conceptual design of the observing systems in AOOS”. These recommendations will be further elaborated in subsequent reports from this project.

3.5 Satellite Broadband in the Arctic

Data transmission by satellite in the Arctic has only been practical for small data quantities because the bandwidth of the service has been limited. Now the user requirements increase for transmission of data in near-real time and two-way communication with the observing platform. Two-way communication is needed for remote control of autonomous observing infrastructure including controlling the sensors operations (e.g. scheduling of the sampling).

There is now a rapid development of new broadband satellite services with global coverage, also including the Arctic region. Research vessels and other ships in the Arctic have started to use [Starlink](#), which is the world's first and largest satellite constellation using a low Earth orbit to deliver broadband internet. Starlink started commercial service in 2021 and as of September 2024 it has more than 7000 small satellites in low orbit and more than 4 mill. subscribers. In July 2024 Space Norway launched two [Arctic Satellite Broadband Mission](#) (ASBM) satellites which will provide continuous broadband coverage north of the 65° N latitude.

These services will facilitate for significant amount of data to be transmitted from a network of observing platforms in any location in the Arctic. The new broadband will also facilitate for realtime data transmission from observing platforms, which will support operational monitoring and secure the data without recovery of the platforms. The research communities should adapt their observing platforms with user broadband communication since these services develop rapidly and will become a crucial part of the observing systems in the coming years.

Figure 3.12. Illustration of the two new Norwegian satellites in the Arctic Satellite Broadband Mission that were launched in a High Elliptical Orbit (HEO).

4. Digitalisation of the ocean

OECD produces a number of documents on science, technology and innovation for a sustainable ocean economy. In a recent publication entitled “[A new era of digitalization for ocean sustainability ?](#)” (OECD, 2021³) the role of digital technologies in the field of ocean observation is explored (Fig. 4.1). Digital technologies are evolving and driving innovation in all parts of ocean observing systems, particularly in sensors, platforms, their autonomy, and system integration. When observational data is used in combination with numerical models and data assimilation, the total amount of data increases in quantity and diversity. In this context digital systems become essential in processing, analysis, visualisation and management of the data, including both observational and simulated data. The digital systems are providing more and more effective tools and services for scientists, managers, companies, educators and other users of the data. Digital technologies such as cloud computing and Artificial Intelligence are evolving rapidly and will impact on all ocean activities dealing with data.

Figure 4.1. Cover page of the OECD report No. 111

In ocean observation there are four areas where technology advancement has generated significant innovation, and digital technologies play a central in all of them. The four areas are:

- (1) Ocean sensing and imaging instruments benefiting from artificial intelligence and machine-to-machine communication
- (2) Expanding spatial coverage of floats, gliders and fixed observation platforms in most of the world’s oceans, except in the ice-covered polar seas
- (3) Mobile platforms (gliders, sailbuoys, small vessels) have increasing autonomy and can operate over larger distances with minimal human intervention
- (4) New complex system integration schemes, with many sensors integrated on the same platform (e.g. seafloor observatories, AUV, ROV) or connected from several platforms, and with connection to subsea cables

In order to implement and sustain the technology advancement in ocean observation a range of measures are required. The costs of scaling-up and innovating ocean observations should be reduced while at the same time new funding sources should be explored. One way to reduce costs is to improve standardization of the data collecting processes and products. The industry-science collaboration

³ This is an adaptation of an original work by the OECD. The opinions expressed and arguments employed in this adaptation should not be reported as representing the official views of the OECD or of its Member countries.

should be expanded by approaching the various offshore industries, telecommunication cable companies, fisheries and aquaculture, tourism and leisure industries.

Further measures proposed by the OECD digitalization report (OECD, 2021) to reduce costs of operating and sustaining an ocean observation network include:

- Leverage existing ocean observation infrastructures and networks, working to strengthen and expand user engagement in already established communities.
- Reduce cost through focusing on low-cost solution where possible and adopting best practices from industry to increase production volumes of sensors and other instruments.
- Expand the coverage of ocean observation networks by increasing collaboration between industry and science to foster more sharing of knowledge, know-how and innovation in observation technologies.
- Improve access to and sharing of data via standardisation, interoperability and best practices, that have a strong potential for considerable cost-savings and efficiency gains.
- Systematically use horizon scanning methods for innovations and existing technologies that might be adapted to support ocean research.

The OECD report (2021) presents several challenges that must be addressed to better exploit the increasing volumes of data resulting from the advances in ocean observing technologies. Among these, data integrity and security are identified as key areas that must be significantly strengthened. Data integrity refers to the accuracy, consistency, and completeness of collected data and how they are processed and quality controlled. Adequate documentation of the lineage of a dataset is essential for users and stakeholders of data and derived products to establish trust in observations, estimates and forecasts, used for decision-making in public and private sectors. Furthermore, improving procedures for ensuring data integrity will support reproducible research. Data security is another critical component in data management frameworks and systems, but research on this topic is underdeveloped. Data security is essential in all stages in the data delivery chain from data collection, transmission, processing, storage and distribution. Thus, more effort is needed to advance both data integrity and security in ocean observation networks, if the scientific, societal and economic benefits of massive investment in digitalisation of the ocean is to be reaped.

The Horizon 2020 project “Integrated Arctic Observation System” (INTAROS) addressed the full data delivery chain from observing sensors to data repositories with focus on in situ observations (Sandven et al., 2022). INTAROS defined a model for the **data delivery chain** describing how data from different observing systems flows through several steps from data acquisition to distribution through open data repositories (Fig. 4.2). It is important to develop this chain into an efficient data delivery stream, enabling users to get easy access to the data.

Standards for geospatial metadata and data formats are complex and therefore time consuming to gain a working knowledge of. While data managers and curators are well versed in documenting and formatting data, they often do not participate in data collection and processing. Scientists and engineers working in the field are experts in their discipline and the technologies used. They have detailed knowledge of the data collected and how processing is carried out, but often have limited expertise in metadata and data standards. Communication between data management and data observation disciplines is hampered by lack of common understanding of each other’s expertise and clear distinction of roles and responsibilities. Therefore, we recommend establishing a mediator mechanism where data managers, scientists and new sensor/platform developers can work together

to adopt and adapt standards for metadata and data to ensure datasets are produced in accordance with the [FAIR principles](#).

Figure 4.2. Data value chains focused for integrating INTAROS data into the various iAOS subsystems (portal, data catalogue, cloud platform, stakeholder applications). (Source: Sandven et al., 2022)

The [INTAROS Roadmap](#) (Sandven et al., 2022) addressed the needs of improving digital solutions for extracting information from the vast amounts of heterogeneous data available from numerous data systems and data providers. This includes, *among others*, satellite remote sensing data, 3D and 4D time series of climate variables from model simulations, predictions and reanalysis, in situ data from fixed and drifting platforms, and in situ data from vessels. Time series of satellite and model data products are typically provided as gridded data, with a common resolution in space and time, and cover large areas such as the North Atlantic or the Barents Sea. In situ data on the other hand are generally available at a much sparser geographical coverage and often with unregular coverage in time, depending on the characteristics of the observing system. The advantages of in situ data include high measurement accuracy and many parameters not observable by other means. This includes for instance observations made below the surface layer of the ocean, deeper than what satellite technologies can observe. Scientific studies, environmental monitoring and management in public and private sectors, as well as other operations in the Arctic Ocean required access to and integration of all available data. As the volume, variety and variability of relevant data sources is complex the need for combining them in a cost-efficient manner introduces several technical challenges. The INTAROS Roadmap stated that cloud technologies can help in accessing, organizing, and processing the massive amounts of data in a scalable and robust manner, without locking into a vendor specific and closed computing environment.

Within a cloud platform, tools for preparing diverse data from different data systems are needed to support efficient integrated analysis. These tools must include methods for transforming data to common formats, aggregation and reprojection to a shared grid (time and space), and quality control of the data (e.g., uncertainty in the data set). Advanced data analysis techniques such as geo-statistics, data assimilation, machine learning and artificial intelligence are needed. However, before applying and customising digital methods, domain experts must define the objective of the integrated analysis, define the workflow for data processing and analysis, and based on this make the choice of suitable computing technology. The development of cloud computing platforms and services is supporting the creation of Digital Twins for different users of environmental data and models. Development of

Digital Twins requires the combined expertise of end users, domain specialists, and technology providers. Achievements of ongoing international Digital Twins projects (e.g. the [Iliad project](#)) and initiatives must be leveraged in the establishment of a sustained Arctic Ocean observing system.

5. Concluding remarks and next steps

There is increasing attention to the Arctic region because climate change is dramatic and has strong impact on environment, resource exploitation and the well-being of people living and working in the region. At the same time, the reduction of sea ice opens up new areas for resource exploitation and shorter shipping routes between Europe, Asia and North America. This will probably lead to more industrial activities with impact on environment and society in a region which is already under pressure. On top of the climate issue the geopolitical situation in the region has changed dramatically, which requires more attention to surveillance and security. The Arctic Ocean is the least explored ocean and new data and knowledge about this region is critical to meet both the climate change and security challenges.

In the UN Decade of Ocean Science (“Havforskningstiåret”) there is focus on developing clean, healthy and productive oceans and support sustainable development of ocean industries. To achieve this goal it is necessary to develop and implement adequate ocean observing systems providing data for monitoring and management of the vast ocean areas. In numerous research strategies for the Arctic, there is focus on establish observing systems and build up databases as foundation for creating new knowledge about the region. The observing systems need to be designed for the coastal regions, the shelf seas and the remote and deep oceans, including the ice-covered Arctic Ocean. Ocean observations are needed in many *public services* (weather-ocean-sea ice forecasting, climate monitoring, environmental monitoring and protection, resource management, ship traffic control, coastguard and defense), *commercial activities* (fisheries, aquaculture, oil and gas, renewable energy, tourism, shipping, insurance) and to achieve policy goals (e.g. “blue economy”, “green shift”, UN Sustainable Development Goals), and last but not least as baseline for *research and innovation* in marine and maritime industries.

Many of the standard ocean observing methods for open ocean cannot be used in ice-covered areas, so there are technological and logistical barriers in collecting data from this region. But the technology development in sensors, platforms, autonomous operations, and integration of different systems is moving forward. This will also be beneficial for the Arctic Ocean, where subsea systems such as moorings, seafloor observatories and drifting floats can be improved and extended to cover larger areas. Argo floats drifting under the ice can be geopositioned if they are equipped with acoustic receivers. Then the profile data can be geolocated after the floats have exited from the ice area and transmitted the data via satellite. Data from moorings can be downloaded and batteries can be recharged by use of AUVs while the moorings are in the water. This means that the moorings can be operational for a longer time and data will be accessible before the moorings are recovered.

Digital technologies are evolving in all parts of ocean observing systems, particularly in sensors, platforms, their autonomy, system integration, and in the processing of the data. The analysis and extraction of useful information from the data can benefit from machine learning and artificial intelligence methods. The data value chain with data sharing and other services for users will be improved.

The adaptation and use of new technologies in to advance the Arctic Ocean observing systems will be further elaborated in report D4: Conceptual design of the observing systems in AOOS and the other subsequent reports due in 2025-2026.

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8. Acronyms

ABSM	Arctic Broadband Satellite Mission
AC	Arctic Council
ACTRIS	Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure, A European infrastructure
AEC	Arctic Economic Council
AECO	Association of Arctic Expedition Cruise Operators
AMAP	Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme
ARCSAR	Arctic and North Atlantic Security and Emergency Preparedness Network
AIS	Automated Identification System
ASM	Arctic Science Ministerial
AUV	Autonomous Underwater Vehicle
CTD	Conductivity, Temperature and Depth instrument
EC	European Commission
ECV	Essential Climate Variables
EEA	European Environment Agency
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EISCAT	European Incoherent Scatter Scientific Association
EPB	European Polar Board
EOV	Essential Ocean Variables
EPCO	European Polar Coordination Office
ESA	European Space Agency
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
EUNIS	Habitat classification system https://eunis.eea.europa.eu/habitats.jsp
Eumetsat	European Meteorological Satellite Organisation
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable og Re-usable
FOO	Framework for Ocean Observing
FSOI	G7 Future of the Seas and Ocean Initiative
GCOS	Global Climate Observing System
IABP	International Arctic Buoy Programme
IASC	International Arctic Science Committee
ICARP	International Conference on Arctic Research Planning
ICES	International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observing System
IMO	International Maritime Organisation
IMB	Ice Mass Balance buoy
INTAROS	Integrated Arctic Observation System – H2020 project from 2016-2022
IPY	International Polar year
ITP	Ice Tethered Profiler
JRC	Joint Research Centre

JRCC	Joint Rescue and Coordination Center
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
NAEAS	Northeast Atlantic Environment Strategy
OECD	In intergovernmental organization that promotes economic progress and world trade.
OSPAR	Oslo-Paris convention for protecting the marine environment in the northeast Atlantic
PAME	Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment
RI	Research Infrastructure
ROV	Remotely Operated Underwater Vehicle
SAR	Search and Rescue
SAON	Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks
SCAR	Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research
SIOS	Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observation System
SME	Small and Medium size Enterprise
UNIS	University Centre in Svalbard
WHOI	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
WMO	World Meteorological Organisation